

LANDSCAPE AND ECOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF BIODIVERSITY ON BAIKAL SIBERIA SPECIALLY PROTECTED NATURAL AREAS

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Abstract: *In article a landscape and ecological analysis of 45 protected areas of various levels was carried out for Baikal Siberia. Most of them (68.8%) are located in the Russian part of the Baikal Lake basin, 11.1% are a Nature Reserves (Zapovedniks), 6.7% - National Parks and 51.1% - Wildlife Reserves (Zakazniks). The Mongolian part accounts for 8.9% of specially protected natural territories, of which 15.5% are National Parks, and 6.7% - Natural Reserves according to the international classification - areas of strict protection, similar to Russian Zakazniks. The distribution of specially protected natural areas is very uneven. Most of the protected areas provide a protective regime mainly of the Baikal natural complexes, where mountain-taiga and forest-steppe landscapes predominate, to a lesser extent - steppe, mountain-tundra, alpine type, mountain-desert. In Transbaikalia, forest-steppe complexes are not affected by protection, especially in the Selenga and Khilok rivers valleys. The high-altitude belt is preserved only around Baikal Lake and on the periphery - in the Mongolian part and in the Tunka Valley. The landscapes of all protected areas, especially those confined to mountain ranges, are characterized by a developed mosaic and the presence of landscape ecotones due to a pronounced altitude belts.*

Thus, there is a need to expand the network of protected areas in the very center of Baikal Siberia, including steppes, forest-steppes and mountain taiga, which form the basis of its ecosystem diversity. At the same time, heterogeneous landscapes should be included in transition (ecotonic) zones. Such an approach is mandatory when designing the "Selenginskaya Dauria" Steppe Reserve on the basis of the Borgoisky State Biological Reserve (Dzhidinsky District, Buryat Republic), the creation of which was planned in accordance with the "Concept for the development of a system of specially protected natural areas of federal significance for the period up to 2020" and the "Action Plan for its implementation" approved by the decree The Government of the Russian Federation (No. 2322-r December 22, 2011), back in 2016.

Keywords: *sustainable development, specially protected natural areas, landscape and ecological zoning, Baikal Siberia.*

INTRODUCTION

The conservation biological diversity problem for the purposes of sustainable (balanced) development, the transition to the called "green" economy, remains relevant for any state and becomes a global trend determining development (sustainability) both individual national economies and the whole Earth. The fundamental "sustainable development", implying the transition from the traditional model of economic growth to the economy of environmental well-being, is the UN Convention on the Conservation of Biological Diversity (Rio de Janeiro, 1992). In 1993 at the Advisory Council on Sustainable Development under the UN Secretary General, the Baikal region was proposed as one of the possible candidates for the title of "global model of sustainable development". In 1995, at the I-th All-Russian Congress of Nature Protection, the Baikal region was finally approved as a model territory for the transition of the Russian Federation to the path of sustainable (balanced) development. In 1996, by the decision of the UNESCO World Heritage Committee, Lake Baikal was recognized as a World Natural Heritage site. In the same year, the project "Comprehensive Program of Land Use policy in the Russian territory of the Lake Baikal basin" was launched (project J. Davis), which confirmed the high status of this unique natural object and covered the territory of three subjects of the Russian Federation – the Buryat Republic, Chita (now the Transbaikalian District) and Irkutsk regions, which are part of the Baikal Natural Territory (Baikal Siberia). The adopted Federal Law of the Russian Federation "On the Protection of Lake Baikal" (No 94-FZ May 01, 1999) defined the legal basis for the protection of Lake Baikal and the

socio-economic development of the Baikal natural Territory on the principles of sustainable development.

In all documents, Baikal Lake is the object of special attention - the oldest, deepest and largest of all the Great rift lakes in the World, whose drainage basin is located in the Asian center on the territory of two states – Russia and Mongolia – between 46°20' -56°40' north latitude and 96°50' -114°10' east longitude. It has an elongated shape from southwest to northeast. The total area of the Baikal basin is 576.5 thousand km². It includes the Lake water area, which is 31.7 thousand km². 44.6% of the catchment area is located within the Russian Federation (in the Buryat Republic 31.8%, in the Trans-Baikalian District 10.2%, in the Irkutsk Region 2.2%, in the Tuva Republic 0.4%), 55.4% of the catchment area is located in Mongolia. About 53% of the volume of river waters is formed in Buryatia, 27% in Mongolia, 16% in the Trans-Baikalian District and 4% in the Irkutsk Region. In general, the Baikal Lake basin due to its geographical and geopolitical location, natural, resource, economic, ethnocultural and personnel potential, as well directly to Baikal, is the main strategic region in eastern Russia and northern Mongolia, the most important foothold for the socio-economic development of the two countries. However, this development has its own specifics due to the special nature management regime in the Baikal basin.

Currently, the rich natural resource potential of the region is intensively used for a wide range of economic purposes and is experiencing anthropogenic impacts that vary in type and degree of impact on the natural environment. Thus, in the Irkutsk region, the main types of environmental management in terms of the strength and area of impact on natural complexes are forest management and an extensive network of industrial and energy enterprises; logging operations is underway in the northern part of Buryatia and in the Trans-Baikalian District, hunting grounds are located and the mining industry is developed (during the development of mining deposits, dumps and tailings ponds are formed, which, despite land use regulations, are practically not cultivated, which leads to landscape degradation, surface and groundwater pollution, and dusty air). In the south of Buryatia and Mongolia, agriculture is the main type of Land use, and in Buryatia it is agriculture and cattle breeding, and in Mongolia on vast steppe areas it is animal husbandry with year-round pasture maintenance [1]. At the same time, the population density and degree of urbanization are low here. By population density, the region is 17 times lower than the global average (53 people/km²). The Russian part of the Baikal basin has a population density of 2.9 people/km² – 9 times less than the European part of Russia (26 people/km²). The urban population makes up 74% of the total population. Urban areas are mainly "near-by-road" territories, with the population concentrated in administrative centers - in Russia these are Irkutsk, Ulan-Ude and Chita. In the Mongolian part of the Baikal basin, only Ulaanbaatar, Orkhon, and Darkhan-uul are highly urbanized. In general, according to these indicators, the Baikal region belongs to sparsely and unevenly populated territories.

In view of this the purpose of work is to analyze the current state of the specially protected natural areas system their further development and optimization, building an ecological framework taking into account the landscape and geographical features of Baikal Siberia.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

In the work, "Baikal Siberia" is understood as a vast area in the center of the Eurasian continent, essentially coinciding with the Baikal Lake catchment. The Land ecosystems of the region were formed in the boundary zone between the Palearctic arid and humid regions and are one of the most important natural boundaries of the temperate zone of Eurasia. In the Southern Siberia mountains, the border of this zone loses its sharp outlines, characteristic of the East-European Plain and forest-steppe regions of the temperate continental climate of Western Siberia, due to the complex composition of the relief and altitude zone.

Baikal Siberia located at the latitudinal junction between two "subcontinents" - North and Central Asia - and in the zone of influence of moisture-bearing atmospheric flows of the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans is a typical example of an ecotonic territory. Earlier, we [2-4] identified a number of factors that contributed to the formation of specific conditions of this zone and peculiar ecosystems of the border type and their fauna.

Firstly, the presence of the transcontinental longitude boundary of the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans influences ensures a high degree of continentality of the climate, as a result of which the potential total evaporation is higher than the annual precipitation, which leads to an imbalance of heat and moisture.

Secondly, due to the predominance of the mountainous terrain, the zonality of natural systems is reduced here, at the same time, the borders of many provinces and sectors are extremely condensed and concentrated. Hollows, large valleys and steep southern exposures of the slopes, exacerbating the lack of moisture, allow the steppes to penetrate far to the north, and the elevated territories, the northern and western slopes of the mountains - to move the taiga far to the south (see the schematic map). As a result, the boundaries between natural areas become very vague.

Thirdly, paleogeographic factors also influenced the modern biogeographic background of contact between the taiga and the steppe, since in the Pleistocene and Holocene there were epochs of significant expansion of the ranges of steppe and taiga landscapes [5,6], anthropogenic transformation of the forest-steppe zone. Together, these factors contributed to the formation of specific ecosystems of the border type here, having a pronounced mosaic character in their spatial structure, which affected the landscape and ecological structure of the specially protected natural areas specially protected natural area, their biological diversity. So, in Baikal Lake has registered more than 2,600 species, of which 84% are endemic. Of particular interest are freshwater sponges, amphipods invertebrates, endemic Baikal seal, the only mammal living in its waters. The flora and fauna of Baikal Siberia were formed at the junction of different biophilotic regions of North and Central Asia, and are distinguished by their diversity and contrast of living communities, from mountain tundra and alpine meadows to dry and desolate steppes (Fig. 1-4). The flora is represented by mountainous, high-altitude, Arctic-alpine, taiga, immoral, swamp, steppe and semi-desert species, has more than 2,500 species (about 1% of the world's total species wealth), endemism accounts for 10% of the total composition. The animal world is also rich and diverse: about 90 species of mammals, about 450 species of birds, more than 20 species of amphibians and reptiles [1].

Cartographic material [7,8] and a landscape map of the region were used to assess and analyze the representativeness of the location of protected areas in Baikal Siberia (Fig. 5).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Currently, 45 protected areas of different levels located in this region, most of which (68.8%) in the Russian part of the Baikal Lake basin to be here. Of these, 11.1% are Zapovedniks, 6.7% are National Parks, and 51.1% are Wildlife Reserves (Zakaznik). In the Mongolian part of high security areas 8.9%, National Parks 15.5%, natural reserves equated to Wildlife Reserves (Zakaznik) according to the international classification, 6.7% [7-9].

The distribution of the specially protected natural areas is very unequally (Fig. 6). Protected areas located in the Irkutsk region (united protected areas "Reserve Pribaikalye", two Wildlife Reserves, Zakaznik) cover almost the entire western Baikal Lake coast along the Primorsky and Baikal'sky ridges, with the exception of a small northwestern part. The largest protected areas on Buryatia (the "Reserve Podlemorye", the Baikal Reserve, two Wildlife Reserves of federal and four republican significance) are also located on the Baikal Lake shores, covering the Barguzin Ridge, the southwestern part of the Ulan-Burgas and Khamar-Daban Ridge with a protected

Figure 1. Mountain tundra of Khamar-Daban Ridge, Baikal Nature Reserve (<https://bolshayastrana.com/bajkaltury-v-yanvareplainSearch=1&dateFrom=2023-01-01&dateTo=2023-01-31®ions=4&sort=price&operatorType=any>).

Figure 2. Taiga belt of the Barguzinsky Ridge, Barguzinsky Nature Reserve (https://vk.com/wall-175862296_75767).

Figure 3. Baikal Lake, Svyatoy Nos Peninsula, Zabaikalsky National Park
(<https://travel.yandex.ru/journal7-dostoprimechatelnostey-buryatii-kotorye-nuzhno-uidet>).

Figure 4. Steppes of Mongolia, Khustain-Nuruu National Park
(<https://www.escapetomongolia.com/traveleastern-mongoliadornod>).

Figure 5. Landscape map of Baikal Siberia [1, p. 69]. Symbols: I. *North Asian Arctic-boreal landscapes*: 1. Char-tundra, sub-char shrubby, larch-sparsely wooded stone birch and dark coniferous-woodlands of the East Siberian type are very low-yielding cold moist habitats; 2. Tundra-meadow and meadow highlands of the South Siberian type are low-yielding cold moist habitats; 3. Mountain-taiga mid-mountain and intermountain depressions larch Baikalo-Dzhugdzhur type conditions of reduced development low-medium productive moderately cold humid habitats; 4. Mountain-taiga mid-mountain and intermountain depressions larch Baikalo-Dzhugdzhur type conditions of limited development medium-highly productive moderately warm moist habitats; 5. Mountain taiga low-mountain and valley larch of the Baikalo-Dzhugdzhur type conditions for optimal development are highly productive in warm, moderately humid and humid habitats; 6. Mountain taiga dark conifers of the South Siberian type in conditions of reduced development of medium-high productive moderately cold moist habitats; 7. Mountain taiga dark conifers of the South Siberian type with limited development conditions are highly productive in moderately warm moist habitats; 8. Mountain taiga dark conifers of the South Siberian type of conditions for optimal development of elevated-highly productive warm moist-excessively moist habitats; 9. Mountain taiga, sub-mountain

and intermountain depressions light coniferous (larch and cedar-larch) of the South Siberian type of conditions of limited development medium-highly productive moderately warm moderately humid habitats; 10. Mountain taiga larch of the South Siberian type of optimal development conditions ("pseudo-taiga") medium-low-yielding warm insufficiently moist-dry habitats;

II. *North Asian semiarid landscapes*: 11 Mountainous and sub-mountain taiga of the Baikal-Dzhugdzhur and South Siberian type, (larch-pine, pine, birch) medium-highly productive warm moderate-insufficiently humid conditions; 12. The sub-mountain and intermountain depressions are meadow-steppe of the South Siberian type, medium-productive in warm, moderately insufficiently humid conditions;

III. *Central Asian Arid landscapes*: 13. Mountainous meadow-steppe and steppe Khangai-Daurian type medium-productive temperate warm dry habitats; 14. Intermountain depressions, sub-mountain and sub-mountain-valley steppe of the Khangai-Daurian type are medium-productive of warm, dry habitats; 15. High plains, denudation plateaus, dry-steppe of the Middle Khalkha Mongolian type, low-yielding, very warm, dry habitats; 16. Low-lying, drainless depressions and lake shores are dry-steppe transitional to the Gobi type of low-minimally productive very warm very dry habitats.

Источник:

https://archive.iwlearn.net/bic.iwlearn.org/bic.iwlearn.org/bic.iwlearn.org/ru/atlas/atlas325a.html?b_start:int=57.

regime. The rest are mostly small, unrelated from the point of view of conservation of biota and landscapes. Thus, the Muisky Reserve is the only and northernmost protected area in Buryatia for the conservation of fauna of the southeastern part of the North Muisky Ridge and the eastern part of the Stanovoy Upland [10]. Also, the only protected area for the Vitim plateau is the Kondinsky Reserve in the Yablonovy Ridge spurs [11]. The Dzherginsky Reserve is located at the junction of the Barguzin, North- and South-Muisky ranges. The Ulyun Reserve on the eastern Barguzin ridge macro slope only partially affects the mountain steppe areas and does not reach the floodplain forests of the Barguzin river valley [12]. The Angirsky Reserve is located in the southeastern Ulan-Burgas ridge. The Khudak Reserve is located separately on the Kurbinsky Ridge.

The Kizhinginsky Reserve is located to the south on the Tsagan-Khurtay Ridge. All of them contribute to the preservation of the mountain taiga and high-altitude complexes, only partially small steppe areas along River valleys (Kizhinginsky and Khudaksky Wildlife Reserves). The steppe and forest-steppe protected areas in Buryatia are a little, all of them are concentrated in intermountain basins - along the tributaries of the Selenga River - Dzhida and Tugnuy. Protected areas in Transbaikalian Region have a small and are aimed at preserving the natural complexes of the Khentei-Chikoysky Highlands (Sokhondinsky Reserve, one federal and one regional reserves) and the Ivano-Arakhley lakes system and the Yablonovy Ridge foothills (one reserve). Together, they make it possible to protect the down and sources rivers [13]. Thus, most of the protected areas provide a protected regime mainly of Pribaikalian natural complexes.

In the Mongolian part of the Baikal Lake basin protected areas are concentrated mainly in the Khangai mountain ranges in the west (1 high security area and 4 national parks) and Khentiy in the east (3 high security areas and 1 national park), including all high-altitude belts of these ranges (fig. 6). Only 3 protected areas (1 national park and 2 Wildlife reserves) are mountain steppe and steppe and meadow valley.

As can be seen, Baikal Siberia is heterogeneous in its landscape representativeness and diversity of biota. As it was shown above, most of it is occupied by mountain-taiga and forest-steppe landscapes, to a lesser extent - steppe, mountain-tundra, alpine-type, mountain-desert. Typical and unique biomes are preserved almost all along the coast of Baikal Lake. The most valuable forest-steppe from the point of view of biodiversity, including expositional ones, are poorly represented in protected areas, especially in the Selenga and Khilok valleys. The high mountain belt is reserved only around Lake Baikal and on the periphery of the studied region - in the Mongolian part and in the Tunka Valley adjacent to the Baikal Lake basin. The greatest landscape diversity is characteristic of

the Baikal-Lena Reserve (29 landscape allotments), the Baikal and Trans-Baikal National Parks (26 and 24, respectively), the Barguzin and Dzherginsky reserves (22 each). Lowland "steppe-forest-steppe" and "wetland" protected areas include an average of 5-6 landscapes. The most "poor" landscapes are again steppe and wetland protected areas: the national park "Khustain Nuruu" in Mongolia and the Kabansky Reserve in the delta of the Selenga River (2 landscape allotments each). The conducted landscape and ecological

Figure 6. The specially protected natural areas (protected areas) of the taiga and steppe contact zone within Baikal Siberia. *Landscape and ecological basis (A):* biomes of the Asian part of Eurasia (according to **A.G. Voronov, 1987**; p. 187[14]). *Protected areas (B):* Nature reserves (Russia)

and strictly protected areas (Mongolia) - 1. Baikal-Lensky; 2. Baikalsky; 3. Barguzinsky; 4. Dzherginsky; 5. Sokhondinsky; 6. Bogdkhan uul; 7. Otgon Tenger; 8. Khan Khentiy; 9. Khordol Sardag; National Parks – 10. Zabaikalsky; 11. Pribaikalsky; 12. Tunkinsky; 13. Noen Hangai; 14. Tarvagatai nuruu; 15. Terelj; 16. Hangain nuruu; 17. Khevsgel; 18. Khorgo; 19. Khustain Nuruu; Nature reserves (Russia) and natural reserves (Mongolia) – 20. Altacheisky*; 21. Angirsky; 22. Atsinsky; 24. Borgoisky; 25. Burkalsky*; 26. Butungarsky; 27. Verkhne-Angarsky; 28. Ivano-Arakhleisky; 29. Irkutsky; 30. Kabansky*; 31. Kizhinginsky; 32. Kochergatsky; 33. Kurtunsky; 35. Prybaikalsky; 36. Snezhinsky; 38. Tugnuysky; 39. Uzkolugsky; 40. Ulunsky; 41. Frolikhinsky*; 42. Khudaksky; 43. Enkhaluisky; 44. Bathaan; 45. Nagal haan; 46. Hogno haan (the distribution of protected areas is given by **T.P. Savenkova, 2002**, p. 21[8] with changes). A UNESCO World Natural Heritage Site is highlighted with hatching.* - Federal Nature reserves (Zakazniks).

division of protected areas of Baikal Siberia showed that according to two or three predominant landscapes in certain reserved areas, it is possible to distinguish protected areas of "large mountain systems of Baikal Siberia with a predominance of mountain taiga" - 34 (75.5% of all protected areas), "steppe and forest-steppe" - 7 (15.5%), "wetlands" - 3 (6.6%). And finally, "steppe protected areas

with wetland landscapes" is the only one in Baikal Siberia (2.2%). The landscapes of all protected areas, especially those confined to mountain ranges, are characterized by a developed mosaic and the presence of landscape ecotones due to the pronounced altitude zone.

CONCLUSION

Thus, there is a need to expand the network of protected areas in the very center of Baikal Siberia, including steppes, forest-steppes and mountain taiga, which form the basis of its ecosystem diversity. Despite the active use of natural resources in the Lake Baikal basin, areas of the natural environment have been preserved in pristine or little-modified condition. There are also territories that have been significantly changed by human activity, but have not lost their attractiveness and significance. The tasks of conservation, maintenance, or restoration of natural complexes carried out by the current network of protected areas are the most significant form of nature protection in the region. It is the territorial principle of conservation with a landscape-ecological approach that should become the basis for the concept of the ecological framework of the Baikal basin that does not yet exist. The development of the existing network of protected areas by expanding it to a certain percentage of the area ratio in today's situation does not allow us to solve this problem. The problem of optimal sizes of individual protected areas and their total area for the conservation of biotic diversity is still debatable [15, 16]. Apparently, it is more expedient to rely on the already existing protected areas of federal significance, provided that their activities are optimized, create protected areas at the regional level and develop environmentally acceptable forms of rational nature management in the territories adjacent to them. When designing new protected areas, it is necessary to take into account the unequal degree of economic development of the Baikal basin and the coverage of the network of protected areas, as well as possible differences in the goals and objectives of conservation, depending on the need to preserve unique objects, the most significant in terms of biotic and landscape diversity of sites and representative territories in various parts of Baikal Siberia. As we noted earlier [2], in transition zones, which is the region under study, it is necessary to include heterogeneous landscapes in their composition as the basis for preserving the biological diversity of protected ecosystems.

The paradigm of further development of the protected areas system should be the creation of recreational areas, primarily natural parks of regional importance. They will act as an alternative to the industrial development of the region, as a buffer for existing protected areas, and as connecting elements of the ecological framework of the Lake Baikal basin. New protected areas are emerging independently in different parts of the Baikal region and in the border territories. So, in 1999, the Alkhanai Nature Park (Zabaikalsky Krai) was established, in 2010. - The Shumaksky Nature Park of Regional significance in the Okinsky district (Republic of Buryatia), in 2011 – the State Nature Reserve of Federal significance "Dzerena Valley" (Trans-Baikal Territory). The federal reserves "Kabansky" (since 1985) and "Altacheisky" (since 2012) now function as branches of the Baikal State Natural Biosphere Reserve, "Frolikhinsky" (since 2009) has been transferred to the protection of the Barguzin Reserve. In 2011 The Barguzin State Natural Biosphere Reserve, the oldest in Russia, and the Zabaikalsky Natural National Park have been reorganized into the Federal State Budgetary Institution "Zapovednoe Podlemorye" with the creation of a joint directorate of these protected areas. Together with the Frolikhinsky reserve, its total length along the coast of the Baikal Lake is over 250 km long [17]. According to the "Concept of development of the system of protected areas of federal significance for the period up to 2020" and the "Action Plan for its implementation" approved by the Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation (No. 2322-r December 22, 2011) in 2016. It was planned to create the "Selenginskaya Dauria" Steppe Reserve on the basis of the Borgoisky State Biological Reserve (Dzhidinsky district, Buryat Republic). Since 2014, work has been underway to justify raising the status of this reserve with the expansion of its territory towards Mongolia and the creation of a transboundary protected area on its basis [18-22].

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